

Supplementary Material

Microbial foaming dynamics in full-scale WWTP anaerobic digesters

Maycoll Romero-Güiza ^{a*}, Miriam Peces ^b, Ruben Asiain-Mira ^c, Jordi Palatsi ^{a**} and Sergi Astals ^b

^a Aqualia, Production Area. Camí Sot de Fontanet, 29. 25197, Lleida, Spain

^b University of Barcelona, Martí i Franquès, 1, Barcelona, 08028, Spain

^c Aqualia, Innovation and Technology Department. Av. Del Camino de Santiago 40. 28050, Madrid, Spain

(*maycollstiven.romero@fcc.es; **jordi.palatsi.civit@fcc.es)

Table 1S. Technical specifications of antifoam agent BURST PF 13T

Chemical nature	Fatty Alcohol Alkoxylate, EO/PO
Form	liquid
Appearance	clear to slightly liquid
Water content	max. 0.5 %
Viscosity (at 23 °C)	130 mPa·s
Density	approx. 0.97 g/cm ³
pH	approx. 7
Setting point	approx. -5 °C

Figure 1S. Sludge characteristics: (A) solids content of the thickened primary sludge (PS, $\text{g}_{\text{TS}} \text{kg}^{-1}$), (B) solids content of the thickened WAS (WAS, $\text{g}_{\text{TS}} \text{kg}^{-1}$), and (C) solid content of the mixed sewage sludge (SS, $\text{g}_{\text{TS}} \text{kg}^{-1}$).

Figure 2S. Anaerobic digesters operational parameters and performance over time. **(A)** hydraulic retention time (HRT, d), **(B)** organic loading rate (OLR, kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹), **(C)** organic matter removal (VS_{removed}, %), **(D)** methane yield (Nm³CH₄ kg⁻¹VS d⁻¹), and **(E)** temperature (T, °C).

Figure 2S_{bis}. Anaerobic digesters operational parameters and performance over time. **(F)** Biogas flow (Nm⁻³ d⁻¹), **(G)** Methane in biogas (%), **(H)** Alkalinity Ratio (IA/TA), and **(I)** pH.

Figure 3S. A) PCA plot of the total microbial community of the AD. Each point represents a sample, crosses represent microbial species showing more variance during the sampling campaign. **B)** Colours differentiate the seasons of the northern hemisphere (winter, spring, summer and autumn).

A

B

C

Figure 4S. Heatmap of the explained variance in (A) fermentative-hydrolyzers, (B) syntrophic acetogens and (C) methanogens communities dynamics based on available operational parameters.

Figure 5S. Centrate parameters. **(A)** Total Nitrogen (TN, mgN L^{-1}), **(B)** Total Phosphorous (TP, mgP L^{-1}), **(C)** Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$), and **(D)** Total Alkalinity ($\text{mgCaCO}_3 \text{L}^{-1}$).

Figure 6S. Correlation between relative abundance of “migrating” species in activated sludge and AD samples.

PAO species abundance in activated sludge and TP in sludge dewatering liquor

PAO species abundance in activated sludge and OLR to AD

Figure 7S. (top) PAO relative abundance in the AD samples and correlation with the concentration of TP in the centrate of dewatered digested sludge and **(bottom)** PAO relative abundance in the activated sludge samples linked with the OLR.

Activated sludge foam in P1

Activated sludge foam in P3

Figure 8S. Foam microscopy images of P1 and P3 foam samples

Figure 9S. BMP specific methane production curves of the experiments carried out with P1_{foam} (with high content of *s_midax_s_334*)

Figure 9S_{bis}. BMP specific methane production curves of the experiments carried out with P3_{foam} (with high content of *s_Ca_microthrix_parvicella*)